

Individuals with risk behaviors in the consumption of alcohol in Italian regions

Their number decreased by 24.60% between 2007 and 2020

The Istat-Bes calculates the value of the "alcohol" variable defined as a standardized proportion of 14-year-old people and more who have at least a risk behavior in alcohol consumption on the total of 14-year-old people and more.

1. Ranking of Italian regions for percentage of individuals having a risk behavior in alcohol consumption in 2020

In 2020 Trentino-Alto Adige is in the first place for percentage of individuals with risk behavior in alcohol consumption equal to a value of 23.4 units, followed by the Aosta Valley with a value of 23, and Molise with a value of 22.6 units. In the middle of the standings there are Piedmont and Basilicata with a value of 17.8 units, followed by Liguria with a value of 17.1 units. Lazio close the ranking with a value of 14.2 units, followed by Campania with a value of 11.6 and Sicily with a value of 9.6 units. On average in 2020 the percentage value of the population having risk at risk in alcohol consumption was equal to an amount of 17.94.

2. Ranking of Italian regions for percentage variation of individuals having risk behavior in alcohol consumption between 2007 and 2020

Sardinia is in the first place due to percentage variation of individuals with risk behaviors in alcohol consumption with a value equal to -11.71% equal to an amount of -2.60 units, followed by Emilia Romagna with a value of -13.36% equal to an amount of -3.30 units, and from Trentino -Alto Adige with a variation of an amount of -13.97% equal to a value of -3.80 units. In the middle of the standings there are Abruzzo with a value equal to -22.82% equal to an amount of -4.70 unit, followed by Veneto with a variation equal to an amount of -24.18% equal to an amount of -6.60 unit and from the Aosta Valley with a value equal to -24.84% equal to a value of -7.60 units. They close the ranking with a variation of -32.06% equal to an amount of -8.40 units, followed by Campania with a value equal to -36.61% equal to an amount of -6.70 units, and from Marche with a variation equal to an amount of -39.70% equal to a value of -10.70 units.

3. Italian macro-regions

The percentage of individuals with risk behaviors in alcohol consumption decreased significantly in the period between 2007 and 2020 in Italian macro-regions. In northern Italy this percentage decreased from 25.00 up to 19.50 or equal to -5.50 unit equivalent to -22.00%. In Central Italy, the percentage of individuals with risk behavior in taking alcohol decreased from a value of 22.10 in 2007 up to a value of 15.90% in 2020 or equal to a value of -6.20 units equal to an amount of -28.05%. In the South, the percentage of individuals with risk behaviors in the intake of alcohol decreased from 18.80% in 2007 up to a value of 13.70% or equal to an amount of -5.10 units or equal to a value of -

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27.13%. Overall in Italy the percentage of people with risk behaviors in the intake of alcohol went from 22.30% in 2007 up to a value of 16.80% equal to a variation of -5.50 units or equal to -24.66%.

4. K-means algorithm clusterization optimized using the silhouette coefficient

Below is analyzed with a clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized using the silhouette coefficient. The identified Clusters are indicated below::

- Cluster 1: Campania, Calabria, Sicily, Lazio, Puglia;
- Cluster 2: Veneto, Friuli-Venezia Giulia, Tuscany, Emilia-Romagna, Piedmont, Sardinia, Molise, Trentino-Alto Adige, Lombardy, Valle d'Aosta, Liguria, Marche, Abruzzo, Basilicata, Umbria.

Calculating the median of the Clusters appears that the median value of the 1-C1 cluster is equal to 14.2 while the value of the 2-C2 cluster is equal to an amount of 18.5. It follows that $C2 = 18.5 > C1 = 14.2$. From a strictly geographical point of view, it appears that the countries of Central-North Italy tend to be characterized by more risky alcohol intake behaviors compared to the regions of Southern Italy except for Basilicata, Molise, Abruzzo and Sardinia.

5. Network Analysis with Manhattan distance

Through the use of Manhattan's distance it is possible to verify the presence of network structures between the Italian regions. A single complex network structure constituted as follows below is detected or:

- Veneto has a connection with Piedmont having a link value of 0.98;
- Piedmont has a connection with the Veneto equal to 0.98 and with Emilia-Romagna equal to 0.97;
- Emilia-Romagna has a connection with Piedmont equal to 0.97, with Sardinia equal to 0.88, with Lombardy equal to 0.83 and with Tuscany with a link equal to 0.58;
- Sardinia has a connection with Emilia-Romagna with a link equal to 0.88;
- Emilia-Romagna has a connection with Sardinia with a link having a value of 0.88;
- Lombardy has a connection with Emilia-Romagna equal to a value of 0.83 units and with Liguria equal to a value of 0.9 units;
- Tuscany has a connection with Emilia-Romagna with a value of 0.5 units.

6. Conclusions

The analysis carried out shows the reduction of individuals who take on risk behaviors compared to alcohol. A reduction that has been verified in all Italian macro-regions and also in all Italian regions. However, the northern regions tend to be structurally more oriented to have risk behaviors than alcohol. In any case, it should be considered that the reduction of this variable in all regions shows that public campaigns aimed at modifying the behavior of Italians have had the ability to induce people to take on life habits much healthier in the 2000s than at the previous decade.

7. Declarations

Acknowledgment. I want to thank the colleagues of the Lum Enterprise S.r.l. and prof. Costantiello and Laureti of LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro.

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Funding. The authors received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Declaration of Competing Interest. The authors declare that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication and/or submission, and redundancies have been completely observed by the authors.

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9. Appendix

Regioni	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Abruzzo	★ 20,6	★ 21,1	★ 19,4	★ 23,9	★ 21,6	★ 18,7	★ 15,6	★ 17,2	★ 16,1	★ 18	★ 17,4	★ 15,9	★ 16,7	★ 15,9
Basilicata	★ 24,6	★ 24,3	★ 22,2	★ 22,8	★ 17,1	★ 16,7	★ 15,1	★ 16	★ 15,4	★ 17	★ 15,5	★ 17,1	★ 16,4	★ 17,8
Calabria	★ 19,3	★ 19,3	★ 15,4	★ 17,5	★ 14,4	★ 15,9	★ 13,7	★ 12,6	★ 14,6	★ 13,1	★ 13,2	★ 15	★ 13,7	★ 16,1
Campania	★ 18,3	★ 15,1	★ 15,8	★ 15,4	★ 15,5	★ 14,2	★ 14,3	★ 12,2	★ 10,8	★ 12,2	★ 12	★ 11,6	★ 10,7	★ 11,6
Emilia-Romagna	★ 24,7	★ 23,1	★ 23,2	★ 22,3	★ 20,7	★ 19,4	★ 18,9	★ 16,9	★ 18,8	★ 19,8	★ 18,1	★ 19,6	★ 18,8	★ 21,4
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	★ 27,1	★ 26,8	★ 24,2	★ 24,8	★ 25	★ 22,1	★ 21	★ 21,5	★ 22,4	★ 24,1	★ 20,6	★ 20,2	★ 19	★ 22,4
Lazio	★ 18,2	★ 16,8	★ 18,1	★ 18	★ 18,6	★ 13,3	★ 14,4	★ 13	★ 13,4	★ 14,4	★ 14,9	★ 14,2	★ 13,8	★ 14,2
Liguria	★ 23,5	★ 21	★ 21,2	★ 22	★ 19,4	★ 17,9	★ 18,8	★ 15,9	★ 16	★ 19,2	★ 19,6	★ 18,2	★ 18,2	★ 17,1
Lombardia	★ 23,2	★ 22,3	★ 21,5	★ 21,8	★ 21,4	★ 18,8	★ 17,2	★ 17,4	★ 18,5	★ 19,3	★ 19,1	★ 18,6	★ 16,4	★ 18,4
Marche	★ 26,9	★ 20,5	★ 20,5	★ 20,9	★ 17,3	★ 18	★ 16	★ 15	★ 18,9	★ 17,4	★ 20,2	★ 18,1	★ 15,4	★ 16,2
Molise	★ 26,4	★ 25,9	★ 27,3	★ 28,8	★ 26,7	★ 22,5	★ 19,5	★ 18,8	★ 18	★ 18,6	★ 20,5	★ 18,8	★ 17,9	★ 22,6
Piemonte	★ 26,2	★ 22,9	★ 24,3	★ 23,1	★ 24,1	★ 17,7	★ 19,5	★ 19,2	★ 19,5	★ 17,9	★ 17,7	★ 19,3	★ 18,1	★ 17,8
Puglia	★ 22,9	★ 20,8	★ 18,3	★ 17,2	★ 15,3	★ 16,1	★ 13,5	★ 13,9	★ 14,7	★ 14,2	★ 15,6	★ 14,5	★ 14,5	★ 16,3
Sardegna	★ 22,2	★ 22,5	★ 24,2	★ 22,9	★ 20,9	★ 20,5	★ 19,3	★ 19,2	★ 20,8	★ 20,7	★ 18,3	★ 18,2	★ 18,9	★ 19,6
Sicilia	★ 12,8	★ 11,2	★ 12,3	★ 11,7	★ 11,4	★ 13,6	★ 10,8	★ 10,8	★ 10,3	★ 9,2	★ 10,6	★ 9,3	★ 10,9	★ 9,6
Toscana	★ 25,5	★ 24,6	★ 22,8	★ 23,8	★ 20,1	★ 19,5	★ 20,1	★ 17	★ 18,5	★ 19	★ 18,1	★ 19,4	★ 18,4	★ 18,5
Trentino-Alto Adige	★ 27,2	★ 26,4	★ 25,1	★ 27,4	★ 24,5	★ 25,9	★ 24,5	★ 24	★ 21,1	★ 25,6	★ 21,8	★ 23,3	★ 21,5	★ 23,4
Umbria	★ 22,8	★ 23,1	★ 20,7	★ 18,1	★ 16,6	★ 15,1	★ 16,8	★ 15,3	★ 15,7	★ 14,8	★ 18,3	★ 18,3	★ 17	★ 16,2
Valle d'Aosta	★ 30,6	★ 27,6	★ 30,9	★ 31	★ 28,7	★ 24,6	★ 25,5	★ 23,4	★ 24,3	★ 27,3	★ 22,8	★ 26,4	★ 25,8	★ 23
Veneto	★ 27,3	★ 23,9	★ 25,2	★ 25,7	★ 22,6	★ 20,2	★ 19,7	★ 20	★ 20,6	★ 18,5	★ 19,6	★ 21	★ 18	★ 20,7

Macro-Regioni	2007	2020	Var Ass	Var Per
<i>Nord</i>	25,00	19,50	-5,50	-22,00
<i>Centro</i>	22,10	15,90	-6,20	-28,05
<i>Mezzogiorno</i>	18,80	13,70	-5,10	-27,13
<i>Italia</i>	22,30	16,80	-5,50	-24,66

Rank	Regioni	2020
1	<i>Trentino-Alto Adige</i>	★ 23,4
2	<i>Valle d'Aosta</i>	★ 23
3	<i>Molise</i>	★ 22,6
4	<i>Friuli-Venezia Giulia</i>	★ 22,4
5	<i>Emilia-Romagna</i>	★ 21,4
6	<i>Veneto</i>	★ 20,7
7	<i>Sardegna</i>	★ 19,6
8	<i>Toscana</i>	★ 18,5
9	<i>Lombardia</i>	★ 18,4
10	<i>Piemonte</i>	★ 17,8
10	<i>Basilicata</i>	★ 17,8
11	<i>Liguria</i>	★ 17,1
12	<i>Puglia</i>	★ 16,3
13	<i>Umbria</i>	★ 16,2
13	<i>Marche</i>	★ 16,2
14	<i>Calabria</i>	★ 16,1
15	<i>Abruzzo</i>	★ 15,9
16	<i>Lazio</i>	★ 14,2
17	<i>Campania</i>	★ 11,6
18	<i>Sicilia</i>	★ 9,6

% di Individui a Rischio nel Consumo di Alcol

**Variazione degli Individui con Comportamento a
Rischio nel Consumo di Alcol tra il 2007 ed il 2020**

Rank	Regioni	Var Ass	Var Per
1	<i>Sardegna</i>	★ -2,60	★ -11,71
2	<i>Emilia-Romagna</i>	★ -3,30	★ -13,36
3	<i>Trentino-Alto Adige</i>	★ -3,80	★ -13,97
4	<i>Molise</i>	★ -3,80	★ -14,39
5	<i>Calabria</i>	★ -3,20	★ -16,58
6	<i>Friuli-Venezia Giulia</i>	★ -4,70	★ -17,34
7	<i>Lombardia</i>	★ -4,80	★ -20,69
8	<i>Lazio</i>	★ -4,00	★ -21,98
9	<i>Abruzzo</i>	★ -4,70	★ -22,82
10	<i>Veneto</i>	★ -6,60	★ -24,18
11	<i>Valle d'Aosta</i>	★ -7,60	★ -24,84
12	<i>Sicilia</i>	★ -3,20	★ -25,00
13	<i>Liguria</i>	★ -6,40	★ -27,23
14	<i>Toscana</i>	★ -7,00	★ -27,45
15	<i>Basilicata</i>	★ -6,80	★ -27,64
16	<i>Puglia</i>	★ -6,60	★ -28,82
17	<i>Umbria</i>	★ -6,60	★ -28,95
18	<i>Piemonte</i>	★ -8,40	★ -32,06
19	<i>Campania</i>	★ -6,70	★ -36,61
20	<i>Marche</i>	★ -10,70	★ -39,78

Variazione Assoluta degli Individui con Comportamento a Rischio nel Consumo di Alcol tra il 2007 ed il 2020

Con tecnologia Bing
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Variazione degli Individui con Comportamento a Rischio nel Consumo di Alcol tra il 2007 ed il 2020

	2020	Regioni	Cluster	Silhouette
1	17.8	Piemonte	C2	0.666059
2	23.0	Valle d'Aosta	C2	0.640231
3	17.1	Liguria	C2	0.631455
4	18.4	Lombardia	C2	0.649951
5	23.4	Trentino-Alto A...	C2	0.656592
6	20.7	Veneto	C2	0.67638
7	22.4	Friuli-Venezia G...	C2	0.670443
8	21.4	Emilia-Romagna	C2	0.669196
9	18.5	Toscana	C2	0.669978
10	16.2	Umbria	C2	0.519337
11	16.2	Marche	C2	0.596318
12	14.2	Lazio	C1	0.656293
13	15.9	Abruzzo	C2	0.576861
14	22.6	Molise	C2	0.664056
15	11.6	Campania	C1	0.682487
16	16.3	Puglia	C1	0.612615
17	17.8	Basilicata	C2	0.55965
18	16.1	Calabria	C1	0.665839
19	9.6	Sicilia	C1	0.663445
20	19.6	Sardegna	C2	0.665374

